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Review Paper

A Review on Herbs Used in Herbal Hand Sanitizer

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ABSTRACT

Herbal medicines are the significant part of healthcare throughout the world. Herbal medicines have been utilized as effectual remedies for the prevention and management of multiple health conditions. Hand washing can stop the chain of transmission of deadly microorganisms from the hand to other parts of the body. Hand hygiene is a vital principle and exercise in the prevention and reduction of healthcare-acquired infections. Hand sanitization is the best aid to prevent infections caused by different types of microorganisms. The given review represents that the plants like guava, Tulsi, clove oil, Ginger, Garlic, are showing benefits in hand sanitizer. The herbal hand sanitizer was found to be effective, economical, and safe for regular use, making it a promising natural alternative for hand hygiene, especially in situations where synthetic alcohol-based formulations are undesirable or cause skin irritation. Hand Sanitizer Is The Most Significant Strategy For Preventing The Transmission Of Hazardous Bacteria And Illnesses.

INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), “an alcohol-containing preparation (liquid, gel, or foam) designed for application to the hands to inactivate microorganisms and/or temporarily suppress their growth. Such preparations may contain one or more types of alcohol, other active ingredients with excipients, and humectants.

The emergence of the Corona virus Disease-2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has risen to be a significant

global public health concern and led to extensive use of hand disinfectants given its contagious nature. Hands are the primary mode of transmission of microbes and infections. Hand hygiene is therefore the most important measure to avoid the transmission of harmful germs and prevent the infections. Hand hygiene is the single most important, simplest, and least expensive means of preventing nosocomial infections.

Contaminated hands can serve as vectors for the transmission of microorganisms. Pathogenic

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microorganisms accountable for outbreaks are spread from the hands of the food handler to others when the food handler contaminates his/her hands and then passes the semicroorganisms to consumers via hand contact with food or drinks. The consumer is exposed following the ingestion of these microorganisms, which may cause gastrointestinal illness. Hand contact with ready-to-eat foods represents a very important mechanism by which pathogens may enter the food supply. Food handlers whose work involves touching unwrapped foods to be consumed raw or without further cooking or other forms of treatment have been identified as a particular risk group. To protect the skin from harmful microorganisms and to prevent spreading of many contagious diseases, hand washing is absolutely an important precaution. Hand washing is the act of cleaning the hands with soap and water for the purpose of removing soil, dirt, pathogenic micro

organisms and avoid transmitting transient microorganisms. Food production workers and food service personnel must be taught to use correct hand and fingertip washing by management in preparation for work

Definition

- A Hand Sanitizer, According To The Latest FDA Definition, Is A Supplement Or Alternative To Hand Washing With Soap And Water.
- Hand Sanitizer, Also Known As A Hand Antiseptic Or Hand Rub, Is A Product That Is Applied To The Hands To Remove Common Pathogen In The Hands. Hand Sanitizers Are Usually Available As Foam, Gel, Or Liquid.
- Various Preparation Are Available, Including Gel, Foam And Liquid Solution

Types of Hand Sanitizer:

Most hand sanitizers fall into one of two categories:

- Hand sanitizer without alcohol
- Hand sanitizer with alcohol content

Advantages of Hand sanitizer:

- Saves time Hand sanitizer is faster than washing hands with soap and water.
- Moisturizing properties Many hand sanitizers contain emollients or humectants to help maintain skin hydration.
- Affordable: Hand sanitizer is generally inexpensive and widely available. Accessible:
- Can be used anywhere, anytime, without requiring access to soap and water. Easy to carry: Hand sanitizer is lightweight and portable, making it easy to take on-the- go.
- Quick application: Fast and simple to apply, requiring no water or towels.

Disadvantages of Hand sanitizer:

- Variable efficacy: The effectiveness of herbal hand sanitizers can vary depending on the type and quality of herbal ingredients used.
- Limited antimicrobial spectrum: Herbal hand sanitizers may not be effective against all types of microorganisms, such as norovirus or *Clostridioides difficile*.
- Shorter shelf life: Herbal hand sanitizers may have a shorter shelf life due to the natural ingredients used, which can degrade over time.
- Skin irritation: Some herbal ingredients can cause skin irritation, such as allergic reactions or contact dermatitis.
- Interactions with medications: Certain herbal ingredients can interact with medications, such as blood thinners or diabetes medications.

The compound, n-propanol, is the most commonly used alcohol compound in biocides[13]. It is not known with much confidence the exact mechanism of alcohol's antimicrobial activity; however, it may be related membrane damage, and inhibition or uncoupling of mRNA and protein synthesis through effects on ribosomes and RNA polymerase[14] or associated with protein denaturation[13]. For activity against bacteria, its optimal bactericidal efficacy is achieved at concentrations between 60% and 90%[15]. In fact, absolute alcohol, or alcohol that is no more than 1% water, is less bactericidal than alcohol. Water is thus critical in the protein denaturation process, if not multiple, are affected by alcohol, essential metabolic pathways, membrane damage and loss of cellular integrity ultimately occur. However, alcohols exhibit bactericidal activity against vegetative bacteria-those undergoing metabolism and binary fission but not against spores.

Mechanism of Action:

Herb's Used In Hand Sanitizer

Sr. No.	Name of Herb's	Synonym	Family	Uses	Image of Herb's
1	Tulsi	Ocimum Sanctum	Lamiaceae	Antibacterial Insecticidal Stimulant Aromatic Spasmolytic	

2	clove-oil	Syzygium Aromaticum	Myrtaceae	Acne Bruises Keeping Infection Mouth Sores Vomiting	
3	Guava leaves	psidium guajava	Myrtaceae	Cholesterol Diabetes Anticancer Antibacterial Gastric	
4	Garlic	Allium Sativum Linn	Amaryllidaceae	Antimicrobial Antihypertensive Antioxidant	
5	Ginger	Zingiber officinale	Zingiberaceae	Antioxidant	

Benefits of Hand Sanitizer:

Cleaness:

- Hand Sanitizer When Used Correctly, Can Kill 99.9% Of Germs On Your Hands. It Is Recommended That You Wash Your Hands Whenever You Are Near Food, Animals, Trash And That Is Just The Tip Of The Iceberg.

Portability :

- A Hand Sanitizer Is An Excellent Choice For Protecting Your Hands From Germs Throughout The Day.

- Keep A Bottle In Your Pocket Or Briefcase For When You Come Into Contact With Public Surfaces.
- There Will Be No Place For You To Wash Your Hands Before Eating At A Food Vendor. Having Your Hand Sanitizer Allows You To Clean Your Hands Before Eating.

Ideal For Group Setting :

- When Soap And Warm Water Are Unavailable, There Are Numerous Advantages To Using Hand Sanitizer.
- You Will Not Only Lower Your Risk Of Infection, But You Will Also Spread Fewer

Germ To Others And Miss Fewer Days At Work.

- When It Comes To The Effectiveness Of Keeping Sanitizer In The Office, The Numbers Don't Lie.

Decreases Risk of illness :

- Limiting Your Exposure To Other People's Germs Is Especially Important During Flu Season.
- Each Time You Take A Break During The Day, You Reduce Your Chances Of Becoming Ill.
- Even A Quick Trip To A Friend's House Or The Store Can Expose You To Germs That Can Cause A Cold, Flu, Or Other Diseases,
- So Keeping Your Hands As Clean As Possible Is Critical. The Ability To Kill Pathogens On Your Hands
- Can Mean The Difference Between Infecting Someone You Care About With Germs And Keeping Your Family Safe. In Certain Circumstances, Alcohol-Based Hand Sanitizers Can Rapidly Reduce The Number Of Microorganisms On Hands.

Good For Sensitive Skin :

- Certain Hand Soap Formulas Can Irritate Sensitive Skin, Which Is A Common Complaint. Commercial Grade Soaps Found In Public Restrooms May Contain Ingredients That Cause Skin Rashes Or Itching. For Sensitive Skin, Hand Sanitizer Is Usually Preferable, Especially If You're Making Your Recipe.

Precaution while using Hand Sanitizer:

- Take Care Of Your Child When They Are Using Hand Sanitizer.
- Keep Hand Sanitizer Out Of Toddler And Children's Reach Because Its Colour And Fragrance Can Allure Our Kids To Drink It.
- Avoid Touching Your Eyes Or Mouth Immediately After Using Hand Sanitizer, And Wait Until Your Hands Are Dry Completely.
- Keep The Hand Sanitizer In A Cool And Dry Place.
- Don't Place Sanitizer In Closed Places Like The Car Because The Alcohol Content In Sanitizer Makes It Flammable And, Keeping Sanitizer In The Car For Hours Or Days Can Create A Risk Of Fire. Hand Sanitizer Contains Alcohol, So It Is Highly Inflammatory.
- Completely Dry Your Hand After Using Hand Sanitizer Before Doing Any Work That Exposes
- You To Heat, Open Flame.

CONCLUSION

Nowadays, people are facing various skin-related issues such as dryness, irritation, and allergic reactions due to the frequent use of chemical-based hand sanitizers. These sanitizers often contain high levels of alcohol and synthetic chemicals which can damage the skin barrier and cause long-term side effects. In comparison, herbal hand sanitizers are a better and safer alternative, as they are made from natural ingredients with antimicrobial properties and minimal side effects. The main purpose behind this review was to highlight the effectiveness and safety of herbal-based hand sanitizers as a natural substitute for chemical formulations. By incorporating plant-

based extracts with known antibacterial and antiviral activities, we can reduce the harmful impact on skin health while still ensuring proper hygiene. Herbal hand sanitizers are a more skin-frien option in maintaining hand hygiene.

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